

Study for dependence of transition state with applied potential in electrokinetic reactions of [Mn-antibiotics-cephalothin] system vis-a-vis kinetics of electrode reactions

Farid Khan

Electrochemical Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. Harisingh Gour University, Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : faridkhan58@yahoo.com; farid.fk@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Polarographic technique was used to study the dependence of 'transition state' with applied potential between dropping mercury electrode and solution interface of [Mn-antibiotics-cephalothin] system at $\text{pH} = 7.30 \pm 0.01$ and $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$ at 298 K. The selected antibiotics were doxycycline, chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline, tetracycline, minocycline, amoxicillin and chloramphenicol together with cephalothin formed complexes with Mn^{2+} . The kinetic parameters viz. degree of irreversibility (λ), transfer coefficient (α), diffusion coefficient (D) and rate constant (k) were determined. The values of α varied from 0.41 to 0.54 (0.05) confirmed that the transition state is affected by applied potential.

Keywords : Transition state, electrokinetic reactions, cephalothin.

In chemical reactions, reactants absorb definite amount of energy as a result of which the free energy derive these reactants from their initial position to the transition state where the reactants cross this energy barrier and form products¹. In electrochemical reactions, free energy is a function of applied potential and applied potential derive oxidants to the transition state and formed reductants. A slide variation of potential affects the rate of the electrochemical reaction and also the rate constant greatly. The aim of the present investigation is to study the dependence of transition state with applied potential for [Mn-antibiotics-cephalothin] system by determining the kinetic parameters and also the complex formation between these antibiotics and Mn^{2+}

Results and discussion

Mn^{2+} gave a well defined two electron quasi-reversible reduction wave in pH range 7.10–8.50 but pH = 7.30 was selected on account of studying the complex system at human blood pH². The pH remains constant during the measurements confirmed that the stability of antibiotics is not altered during the measurements.

[Mn-antibiotics-cephalothin] system :

The values of $E_{1/2}$ became more negative when [cephalothin] = 0.025 M and 0.05 M was added with [Mn-

Fig. 1. Plots between $-[E - RT/nF \log(i_d - i)]/i$ vs i for [Mn-doxycycline-cephalothin] system.

Table 1. Stability constants^a of [Mn-antibiotics-cephalothin] system

[Mn²⁺] = 0.50 mM, pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, T = 298 K

Antibiotics	log β ₀₁	log β ₀₂	log β ₁₀	log β ₂₀	log β ₃₀	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁
Doxycycline	-	-	3.21	4.86	7.15	4.16	5.18	7.63
Chlortetracycline ²	-	-	3.31	5.02	7.78	4.58	5.76	7.93
Oxytetracycline ²	-	-	4.00	-	8.13	4.98	-	8.32
Tetracycline ²	-	-	4.12	7.13	8.20	5.01	7.46	8.46
Minocycline	-	-	4.35	7.48	8.56	-	7.67	8.70
Amoxicillin	-	-	4.51	7.93	8.87	5.30	8.13	9.01
Chloramphenicol	-	-	4.67	8.01	9.12	5.36	8.24	9.31
Cephalothin	1.75	2.65	-	-	-	-	-	-

E_{1/2}^r = -1.40 V. E_{1/2}^q = -1.41 V.

^aThe values of stability constants for others system can be obtained on request.

antibiotics] at pH = 7.30 ± 0.01 in μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄ at 298 K confirmed the formation of [Mn-antibiotics-cephalothin] system. The E_{1/2}^{reversible} values from E_{1/2}^{quasireversible} were obtained by plotting E - RT/nF log (i_d - i)/i against i at i → 0³ (Fig. 1). Schaap and McMaster⁴ method was used to confirm the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes with Mn²⁺ and selected antibiotics (Fig. 2). The values of stability constants are given in Table 1. The values of binary complexes of Mn with minocycline, amoxicillin and chloramphenicol were determined by Deford and Hume method while the [Mn-cephalothin] complexes by Lingane method⁵.

The value of mixing constant log k_m, which compares the stability of binary and ternary complexes, is given by the following equation,

$$\log k_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2[\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{02}]$$

The values of log k_m were 0.40, 0.74, 0.12, 0.01 and 0.03 respectively for [Mn-doxycycline-cephalothin], [Mn-chlortetracycline-cephalothin], [Mn-tetracycline-cephalothin], [Mn-amoxicillin-cephalothin] and [Mn-chloramphenicol-cephalothin] systems showed that ternary complexes were more stable than their binary complexes. In case of [Mn-oxytetracycline-cephalothin] and [Mn-minocycline-cephalothin], the values of log k_m were not calculated owing to the absence of [Mn-(oxytetracycline)₂] and [Mn-minocycline-cephalothin] complexes.

The values of rate constants for a redox system is given by,

$$k_{red} = Z \exp \left\{ \left(\frac{-\Delta G_{red \text{ no voltage}}}{RT} \right) \left(\frac{-\alpha FV}{RT} \right) \right\}$$

where the terms have the usual meanings⁶. The plots

between log (Z - 1) vs (E_{1/2}^{rev} - E) for [Mn-neomycin-cephalothin] system are all straight lines. The values of kinetic parameters are given in Table 2. The values of rate constant depend only on applied voltage. The value of α was 0.50 (varied from 0.41 to 0.54) provides an insight into the way the transition state is influenced by the applied voltage. A value of 0.50 means that the transition state behaves midway between the oxidant and

Fig. 2. [Mn-doxycycline-cephalothin] system.

Table 2. Kinetic parameters of [Mn-doxycycline-cephalothin] systemMn²⁺ = 0.5 mM, pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, T = 25 °C

[Doxycy- line × 10 ³]	[Cephalothin] = 0.025 M						[Cephalothin] = 0.05 M					
	$E_{1/2}^{95\%} - V$ vs SCE	Slope (mV)	α	λ (s ^{-1/2})	$D \times 10^3$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	$K \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)	$E_{1/2}^{95\%} - V$ vs SCE	Slope (mV)	α	λ (s ^{-1/2})	$D \times 10^3$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	$K \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.00	1.4150	37	0.42	2.02	3.82	7.73	1.415	37	0.42	2.02	3.82	7.73
0.50	1.4350	38	0.41	2.69	3.82	10.27	1.4245	36	0.48	1.51	3.82	5.80
1.00	1.4400	36	0.47	1.80	3.75	6.77	1.4400	36	0.54	1.01	3.75	3.81
2.00	1.4500	38	0.44	1.91	3.75	7.17	1.4650	36	0.50	1.35	3.75	5.08
3.00	1.4600	38	0.52	1.07	3.75	4.03	1.4700	37	0.44	1.27	3.69	4.17
4.00	1.4700	38	0.52	1.13	3.69	4.19	1.4750	36	0.48	1.13	3.69	4.19
5.00	1.4705	38	0.52	0.85	3.69	3.14	1.4850	37	0.44	1.20	3.62	4.36
6.00	1.4875	38	0.49	1.07	3.62	3.89	1.4900	38	0.49	1.51	3.62	5.50
8.00	1.4900	38	0.57	0.90	3.62	3.27	1.4950	38	0.57	1.27	3.55	4.54
10.00	1.5110	38	0.46	1.01	3.55	3.60	1.5000	37	0.50	1.20	3.49	4.29
20.00	1.5250	38	0.46	2.40	3.55	8.56	1.5150	36	0.42	1.51	3.49	5.30
30.00	1.5300	36	0.52	1.13	3.69	4.19	1.5200	37	0.50	1.43	3.49	5.00

reductant response to applied potential and it always lies in an exact mid of d.m.e and solution interface. The diffusion coefficient (D) that depends upon the thickness of the diffusion layer was calculated by Ilkovic equation⁵ and its values are given in Table 2. The values of rate constant (k) are as expected and confirm the quasireversible nature of the electrode processes.

The trend in stability constant of complexes was doxycycline < chlortetracycline < oxytetracycline < tetracycline < minocycline < amoxicillin < chloramphenicol. All the tetracycline including doxycycline and minocycline are having the same structures except in the difference in R₁ and R₂ positions. The all made bond with oxygen of 1, C and oxygen of amide (CONH₂) group⁷ at 2, C atom. The doxycycline formed the complexes of minimum stability with Mn²⁺. The lesser stability of chlortetracycline complexes than that of oxytetracycline complexes is due to the presence of more electrons withdrawing Cl at R₁ in the former in place of H in the latter⁸. In case of tetracycline, H is present both at R₁ and R₂ therefore; there is least electronic disturbance in tetracycline in comparison to other tetracycline complexes. The stability of minocycline complexes is lower than that of amoxicillin complexes is owing to the presence of a six-membered ring with two double bonds. The complex with a saturated five membered ring is more stable than a complex with unsaturated six membered ring⁹. In the case of cephalothin, O of the COOH and N of the β-lactam ring took part in bond formation with Mn. The values of

stability constants (log β) varied from 1.7 to 9.31¹⁰.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Mn²⁺, antibiotics and cephalothin were taken in the ratio of 1 : 40 : 40 and current voltage curves were obtained in different pH values. It has been observed that the maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ was observed within the pH range 7.10–8.50, but pH 7.30 ± 0.01 was selected on account of studying the complexes in human blood pH. Ellico-pH meter (Model LI-120) was used to measure the pH of the analyte at 7.30 ± 0.01 adjusted with dilute solutions of NaOH or HClO₄ as required. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate sodium buffer was added to stabilize the pH of the analyte. 0.001% Triton X-100 was used as the suppressor. The current voltage curves were recorded on a manual polarograph using polyflex galvanometer (PL-50). The polarographic cell was of Latinin and Lingane⁵ type in which capillary of 5.0 cm in length with 0.04 mm in diameters was used. The $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}$ value was 2.40 mg^{2/3} s^{1/2} at 60.02 cm effective height of mercury. The resistance of the cell was lesser than 250 Ω therefore, IR correction was not made.

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Note

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